

PROBLEMS IN TRANSLATING ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS EXPRESSING FRIENDSHIP INTO UZBEK.

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Abstract: The aim of the present thesis is to study the linguacultural features of phraseological units of English and Uzbek languages and express friendship in Uzbek language. As a result of experience of comparisons English and Uzbek phraseological units the following ways of translation of phraseological units are distinguished: equivalence-based translation, calque-based translation and descriptive translation.

Keywords: Phraseological units, idiom, national-cultural specificity, linguistic and extra linguistic character, reality, friendship

Translation has been a means of communication between nations and people for many years playing an important role in obtaining information about the culture and many years history of two or more nation representatives. Nowadays the role of translation is increasing in the development of a nation and society too. Through translation, different nations can get an opportunity to get to know about the lifestyle, culture, history and the achievements of the society of a certain country. Each nation has it's certain national peculiarities in their speech which is getting down from generation to generation. Among such peculiarities, onomastic units and phraseological units with onomastic components are inextricably linked with the spiritual culture, customs, profession, living conditions, aspirations, attitude to reality of the people of the certain language.

In English proverbs and sayings, idioms are indispensable part of phraseological units. In Uzbek proverbs and sayings are not part of idioms, but they are an integral part of folklore. Often it seems that proverbs and sayings are very similar to each other. As a saying and a proverb help figurative expression of thought, enrichment of the content of the speech. When studying the difference between proverb and saying becomes clear that proverbs express finished thought, and thoughts unfinished, and that the latter, without expressing to the end of the idea, point to it. Saying no conclusion, morals, it is used to derive any conclusion. For example, the proverb: If you ran after two hares, you will catch neither- ikki kemaga oyoq qo'ygan g'arq bo'lur. No rose without a thorn- gul

tikansiz bulmas. Rome was not built in a day - musulmonchilik astachilik. Saying: Can the leopard change his sports? - bukurni go'r tuzatadi. Except proverbs and sayings has an idiom or stable expression (locution). A stable phrase (locution) is a combination of words with a figurative meaning that expresses a concept or thought. A locution (phraseological unit): It's Greek to me- bu aqlga sigmaydi. To kick the bucket -jon bermoq. The real McCoy- olmosdek qadrli narsa. Linguistic and cultural features of phraseological units in English and Uzbek languages are analyzed. National-cultural features of phraseological units are determined by extralinguistic factors. Under extralinguistic factors is the combination of factors that are important when creating social, economic, cultural prerequisites and conditions for internal structural and functional development of language in the development and education of phraseological units and which serve as prerequisite for submission of national nature.

Issues of translating phraseological units from English into Uzbek, considering their etymological and social attributes, is viewed as quite possibly the most troublesome sorts of interpretation changes. The object of interpretation isn't a language framework as a deliberation, be that as it may, a particular discourse work in another dialect (the first content), based on which another discourse work in another dialect (the interpretation text) is made. The reason for the interpretation is to familiarize the peruser (or audience) who doesn't have the foggiest idea about the first language as intently as conceivable with this content (or the substance of oral discourse). Problems of phraseology are extremely important both for practice and for translation theory; they often present great practical difficulties and arouse great theoretical interest, since they are related to the difference in semantic and stylistic functions performed in different languages by words of the same real meaning, and to the difference in combinations that such words enter into in different languages. This paper discusses only some of the many problems of translating phraseological units. It is usually accepted to indicate the equivalent of a phraseological unit to a word. However, the theory of complete equivalence is becoming obsolete. This does not mean that phraseological units and words have nothing in common, which is considered by the theory of correlation of certain types of phraseological units and words, which, however, is based on slightly different principles. The most characteristic for phraseological turns of stable combinations of words are in principle equal in meaning to a single word, differing from it, as a rule, by a certain expressive and stylistic coloring. Some idioms are translated with the help of partial (relative) equivalence. According to E.F.Arsentyeva, such

idiomatic expressions are characterized by the minor differences in terms of phraseological expression of the identical semantics that can have a componential or morphological character (Arsentyeva, 1989: 100) The classification of phraseological units also contains the necessary theoretical knowledge for the translator, with which we can identify the phraseological units in the text, then analyze it and, based on the analysis, give the most accurate translation in this context. The most legitimate approach is to consider phraseological units in three aspects: semantic, structural grammatical, and component. Taking into account the marked levels, the following types are distinguished: 1) phraseological equivalents (full and partial) - phraseological units with identical semantics, structural and grammatical organization and with identical component composition; Red book - Qizil kitob; The black prince - Qora shahzoda; Black list - Qora ro'yxat; Black diamonds - Qora oltin; Keep quiet - Sir saqlamoq; Make conversation - Manosiz suhbatlashmoq; Milk cow - Sog'in sigir; First think, then speak - Avval o'yla, keyin so'yla; The dog bark, but caravan goes on - It hurar, karvon o'tar; Step by step - Qadam ba qadam.

2) phraseological analogs (full and partial) - phraseological units that express the same or similar meaning, but are characterized by a complete difference in the approximate similarity of the internal form; A black hen lays a white egg - Qora sigir oq sut berar. Cut the melon - foydanib olmoq. Put smb/somth to the test - tekshirib ko'rmoq; Red meat - Qo'y go'shti; Take a fancy to smb - Maftun bo'lmoq; Talk turkey - Ochiqdan-ochiq gapirmoq.

3) non-equivalent phraseological units - phraseological units that do not have correspondences in the phraseological system of another language. To throw up one's cap - do'ppisini osmonga otmoq . Come Yorkshire over smb - Aldamoq, nonni tuya qilmoq Betweenhawk and buzzard - Oila a'zolarini va xizmatkorlar o'rtasidagi o'rinni egallagan inson; Green room - Teatrda artistlarning kiyinadigan, yasanadigan xonasi; Harley Street - Shifokorlar, tibbiyot dunyosi (Lo'ndondagi ko'pgina mashxur doktorlar yashaydigan ko'cha); Gretna Green marriage - Uydan qochgan sevishtanlar o'rtasidagi turmush; Since phraseology stands out for its functions in language and speech, it requires a special approach in the translation process. The main difficulty is that no dictionary can provide for all the false uses of phraseology in the context. Phraseological units, similar in internal form in different languages, are not always identical in meaning as a result of their reinterpretation, so you can not rely on the similarity of the figurative basis. But when an expression still retains its connection with the sphere in which it was born, the translator has to look for

such a phraseological units in the Uzbek language. Techniques for translating phraseological units vary from complete replacement of imagery to complete preservation of the image in translation. And yet, what is common and characteristic of all is the preservation of imagery in translation.

The concept of “friendship” is an abstract notion which is valuable in a human life that take place in the row of social concepts as “family”, “health”, “wealth” and “labour”. Translating proverbs word-by-word is not sufficient way to express the meaning of a proverbs in the other languages because of culturemes that exists in its content in a target language. It may cause to misunderstand the basic meaning of a proverb. Therefore, the method of finding equivalents of proverbs in English and Uzbek is used to investigate peculiarities of proverbs about friendship in these languages. (1) Birds of a feather flock together. – O’xshatmasdan uchratmas (They do not meet who do not look like each other). The behaviour of birds is taken as a resemblance to the human friendship in the English proverb , while a short sentence structure with unknown subject is used in the Uzbek one. It is confessed that a sentence structure in which a subject is elliptical is characteristic of the nearly all proverbs belong to the Uzbek nation. In addition, according to the interesting fact that both proverbs, which are given above have Arabic origin (XVI century). There are many synonym words and phrases in a language, proverbs can be synonymous to one another. Sometimes their meanings are similar and they can substitute one another in a context. However, many of synonym proverbs cannot be absolute synonyms even they resemble one another semantically. Because, expressiveness in their meanings differs in some degree from each other, consequently they are used in different cases and situations – so they own different pragmatic and sociolinguistic features: some of them are mostly applied in formal (official) cases while some of them often appear in informal (oral) conversations. Though the proverbs that given above have several synonyms they cannot substitute one another in a context, otherwise the semantic or stylistic balance would be destructed roughly.

A man is known by the company he keeps. – Do’sting kimligini ayt, sening kimligingni aytaman (Tell me your friend, I shall tell who you are). In these proverbs it is said that man’s qualities are determined by what kind of friends he has. In semantic point of view, these two proverbs seem identical, but their pragmatic features are different: the English proverb is usually used in more formal and literary styles, in its turn the Uzbek one is mostly applied in colloquial speech.

There is no better looking-glass than an old friend. / The eye of a friend is a good mirror. – Do'st achitib gapirar, dushman kuldirib (A friend tells bitter (truth), an enemy sweet (lie)). These proverbs says that a true friend tells reality even you do not like it and they should tell you your mistakes or bad character, while enemies deceive you with sweet words in order to be liked or find your weak point. In these both English proverbs the lexeme of mirror (= looking glass) is used. The Uzbek equivalent of these proverbs has the stylistic device of oxymoron (friend – enemy, bitter – sweet).

A friend in court is better than a penny in purse. – Boylik boylik emas, birlik boylik (Wealth is not wealth, solidarity is wealth). The main meaning of these proverbs represents that friendship is more valuable or necessary than money, it is real wealth. The existence of the cultureme “penny” proves that it belongs to the English nation. The English culture compare friendship with the currency and it says friends are better than pennies; being friends is equalised to real wealth in the Uzbek one.

It is good to have some friends both in heaven and hell. – Do'sting yoningda bo'lsa, ishing oson bitadi (While your friend is with you, you solve your problem fast). The English proverb possesses strong expressiveness and impressiveness because of the culturemes “heaven” and “hell”, at the same time they are religious words and semantic opposites (antonyms). The existence of these words represents the linguocultural and pragmatic peculiarities of this proverb. The proverb in Uzbek has more simple structure and literal meaning in comparison with the English one that owns figurative meaning.

Be a friend to thyself and others will befriend thee. – O'ziga boqmagan, o'zgaga yoqmas (If one does not pay attention to himself (his character or behaviour), others do not like him). There are old forms (“thyself”, “befriend”, “thee”) of English words in the proverb, which belongs to the Old English. It shows that this proverb has long usage by the nation and nowadays it is still being used frequently. Both of these proverbs mean that if a person respects himself and keeps himself from doing bad things, he gets many friends.

Friends are made in wine and proved in tears. – Do'st kulfatda bilinar (A friend is tested in trouble).

To conclude, proverbs come to be a very numerous parts of the English and Uzbek languages. They differ semantically, structurally, stylistically and even pragmatically from one another. Proverbs cover many drawbacks of the culture of a nation. Proverbs serve to describe, define and express the culture of the language in which they exist. One can see national notions, things, feelings,

traditions, well-known ancestors, even the names of places – cultural points in the paremiologic fund of a language. English and Uzbek proverbs connecting with the concept of “friendship” reflects the mentality, culture and traditions of a nation and take important place in the language of this nation. In both languages, proverbs about friends are various, besides synonymous or antonymous proverbs can be found among them. But their synonymic and antonymic relations are not considered to be absolute, because they are chosen according to a context, as a result their meanings may be also slightly changed. Therefore, applying a proverb in an appropriate place makes a speech clear and fluent. Because as it was mentioned above, proverbs are often used in a speech and they are chosen according to time, place, case and other pragmatic factors. Besides, a society and social processes effect directly to the usage, semantic expressiveness and other features of proverbs. The translation process of proverbs from one language into another requires more than componential or structural approach, it is necessary to give exactly main idea of a target proverb in a translation. As the main result of the paper it is proved that the semantic, structural or stylistic similarities are found between English and Uzbek proverbs about friendship as well as they have many differences. But resemblance between linguocultural peculiarities of these proverbs do not occur in these languages. Because they are not relative languages according to the genetic classification of world languages. Furthermore, every nation has its culture, tradition and, of course, culturemes reflecting the parts of the culture in this nation’s language. These culturemes serve to provide original semantic and linguocultural features of proverbs. In the view of the observations made above, it is important to point out that proverbs contain social practices that can be visualized in a real or possible world. Furthermore, a language always changes itself day by day, for that, the quantity of proverbs in it also changes; some proverbs may disappear, people may begin to use some other new proverbs in their conversations.

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